

Unveiling the structural, optical coating and thermoelectric characteristics of kesterite-quaternary chalcogenides $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S}, \text{Se}, \text{Te}$) via DFT study

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the distinctive features of novel kesterite-type chalcogenide semiconductor materials through a new scheme designated as $\text{I}_2\text{-III-III-VI}_4$, focusing on $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S}, \text{Se}, \text{Te}$). The investigation employs density functional theory (DFT) using the advanced all-electron full potential linear augmented plane wave (FP-LAPW) method. The exchange-correlation potential is assessed through the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) parameterization, complemented by the Tran–Blaha modified Becke–Johnson (TB-mBJ) exchange potential estimation. Furthermore, thermodynamic parameters are analyzed in relation to temperature and pressure for the selected materials, utilizing the quasi-harmonic model. The electronic structure analysis reveals that $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S}, \text{Se}, \text{Te}$) materials display semiconducting behavior, with direct band gaps measured at 1.9 eV, 1.1 eV, and 0.86 eV, respectively. Moreover, the predicted refractive index, absorption coefficient, dielectric function, absorbance, transmittance and reflectance revealed that $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S}, \text{Se}, \text{Te}$) are promising materials for photovoltaic and optoelectronic devices. Furthermore, the analysis of thermoelectric properties considering the Seebeck coefficient, thermal conductivity, electronic conductivity, and highly valued figures of merit showed that the studied kesterite-type compounds have strong potential for applications in the fields of thermoelectric power energy. Finally, all these results are considered favorable and appropriate as per the characteristics mentioned earlier, and their potential advantages and applications in advanced hybrid photovoltaic and thermoelectric systems have been highlighted. It has been declared that this study's attained results were considered a prediction in this kesterite family.

1. Introduction

In recent years, quaternary chalcogenides of the $\text{I}_2\text{-II-IV-VI}_4$ family have been extensively studied, especially in the optoelectronic field, due to their peculiarity [1–4]. In this paper, the new chalcogenide

semiconductor compounds have been explored with a new scheme $\text{I}_2\text{-III-III-VI}_4$ [I: Ag, III: In, Ga and VI: S, Se, and Te], which represents a deviation from the traditional framework $\text{I}_2\text{-II-IV-VI}_4$ compounds. Most quaternary chalcogenide compounds have most of the earth-abundant components and these materials have precisely tunable

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physical properties for which they have been coveted in various fields and have been proven to be good candidates in both scientific [5–11] and industrial applications [12–27]. Hence, numerous quaternary chalcogenide compounds that belong to the $I_2-II-IV-VI_4$ family have been investigated, allowing the formation of thousands of quaternary chalcogenide compounds [1]. Among them, specifically, copper-zinc-tin selenide $Cu_2ZnSnSe_4$ (CZTSe) and copper-zinc-tin-sulfide Cu_2ZnSnS_4 (CZTS), which were fascinated by tremendous observation in solar cells implementation due to their suitable optical features such as a desirable direct band gap of around 1.5 eV and tunability of the semiconducting properties by alloying various elements [28–31]. Most efforts have been made to design the optimized device structure that can accommodate current CZTS absorbers and help the development of sustainable photovoltaic technology [32,33]. Despite their impressive efficiencies, CZTS compounds suffer from stability issues that require further research. A series of other quaternary chalcogenide compounds with the formula $I_2-III-III-VI_4$ have been suggested numerically by Mengwei Gao et al. [34], and they showed elemental properties extracted from Wolfram programming language, as well as 2180 quaternary semiconductor compounds with a band gap energy array from 1.6 eV to 3.2 eV. In addition, they calculated the electronic features, including the density of states and band structure for the Ag_2InGaS_4 compound, using the HSE06-DFT method, and found bandgap energy equal to 1.72 eV. This family of compounds is close to CZTS. On the other hand, these materials have been found in several polymorph crystal structures such as stannite ($I4^-2 m$), kesterite ($I4^-$), sphalerite (zinc blende, Fm) and PMCA (primitive mixed CuAu-like, $P4^-2 m$) at high temperatures. According to research related to the structural stability of CZTS, kesterite has been found the most stable phase [1,36–41].

This motivates us to investigate the different physical properties of three quaternary chalcogenides Ag_2InGaX_4 ($X = S, Se, Te$) in the kesterite structure using the abinitio FP-LAPW method [42,43] implemented in the Wien2k code [44]. For the exchange-correlation potential, the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) generalized gradient approximation (GGA) [45] and the Tran Blaha modified Becke–Johnson (TB-mBJ) approach [46] has been chosen for more electronic eigenvalues accuracy [47,48]. Nevertheless, due to a lack of studies and research on these types of compounds $I_2-III-III-VI_4$ in kesterite structure, a comparative study together has been performed with their homologous succession of kesterite light absorber materials CZTX ($X = S, Se, and Te$) [36–41] to better understand their properties. The obtained results of the optical thin film characteristics and thermoelectric parameters description have been considered valuable additions and are of considerable significance for the area of hybrid photovoltaic thermal systems, photovoltaic systems, and optoelectronics devices' applications.

2. Computational methods

The first-principles evaluations were attempted to thoroughly examine the geometry optimization, structural, thermodynamic, optoelectronic and thermoelectric characteristics of the kesterite structure for the selected chalcogenide semiconductor compounds with the new scheme $I_2-III-III-VI_4$ [I:Ag, III:In, Ga and VI: S, Se, and Te]. All the calculations have been performed with the help of the full-potential linear-augmented-plane-wave (FP-LAPW) plus local-orbital technique inside the density functional theory framework [42,43], prosecuted in the WIEN2K code [44]. The exchange-correlation issues were considered with the help of the GGA, assuming PBE parameterization [45]. In addition, we include the Tran–Blaha modified Becke–Johnson (TB-mBJ) exchange potential approximation [46] to get more precise electronic wave functions [47,48]. Moreover, to attain a reasonable convergence, the keystone set for self-consistent field evaluations is within 10^{-5} Ry of the entire energy of the system, and a plane wave cut-off of kinetic energy $R_{mt} \times K_{max} = 7.0$ has been nominated for Ag_2InGaX_4 ($X = S, Se, Te$). The muffin tin radii for Ag, In, and Ga have been disposed to 2.0, 2.2, and 2.0 Bohr, respectively, whereas for S, Se, and Te, the muffin tin radii

are taken to 1.6, 2.0, and 2.2 Bohr, respectively. For the K-blending over the Brillouin zone [49], a mesh of $6 \times 6 \times 6$ has been selected in the Brillouin zone, which corresponds to 35 k -points for structural and electronic calculations, while a mesh of 2562 k -points ($27 \times 27 \times 27$) in the complicated illustrations have been utilized for the calculation of the optical and thermoelectric features. Finally, the valence electrons contain the 4d and 5s orbitals for Ag and In and the open-shell s and p orbitals for S, Se and Te.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural features

It is known that the Ag_2InGaX_4 ($X: S, Se, Te$) compounds belong to the CZTS family of compounds. The first principles demonstrated that these compounds are the most stable in kesterite structure, which has the lowest binding energy [1,28–31]. Therefore, we focus on the physical features of the suggested materials Ag_2InGaS_4 , $Ag_2InGaSe_4$, and $Ag_2InGaTe_4$ in kesterite structure that possesses tetragonal unit cell with space group $I-4^-$ (space group: 0.82) (displayed in Fig. 1), where the Wyckoff locations in the conventional unit cell have been optimized as presented in Table 1. In this research, the calculations performed by the PBE-GGA approximation [45] as implemented within Wien2k [44]. Our results of the structural properties have been provided in the non-magnetic state for three chosen quaternary chalcogenide compounds Ag_2InGaX_4 ($X: S, Se, Te$). The values of the c/a ratio have been found for selected materials Ag_2InGaX_4 ; after that, the volume optimization of the kesterite unit cell has been investigated for Ag_2InGaX_4 . The fluctuation of the entire energy-dependent volume is carried out and the curve is fitted to the equation of state (EoS) of Birch–Murnaghan [50–52] for finding the different equilibrium parameters of the unit cell like: lattice parameters a and c , equilibrium bulk modulus B_0 and pressure derivative of bulk modulus B' , equilibrium volume V_0 and the equilibrium total energy (E_0). All optimized lattice parameters have been listed in Table 2. The fluctuation of the entire energy as a function of the volume of the selected kesterites is visualized in Fig. 2.

Because there are no studies on the growth mechanism available for the selected kesterite Ag_2InGaX_4 ($X: S, Se, Te$) in the literature, our results on these materials are a fulfilled prediction. However, this does not prevent us from comparing results between the compounds. As

Fig. 1. Crystal structure of the kesterite Cu_2ZnSnS_4 (CZTS).

Table 1
Wyckoff positions of $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X: S, Se and Te).

Atom	Wyckoff positions	x	y	z
In	2b	0	0	0.5
Ga	2c	0	0.5	0.25
Ag1	4a	0	0	0
Ag2	4f	0	0.5	0.75
S	8e	0.2224	0.2646	0.3688
Se	8e	0.2352	0.2637	0.3691
Te	8e	0.2456	0.2621	0.3698

commonly seen in chalcogenide type compounds, like CZTX (with X = S, Se and Te) the popular used materials in thin film solar cell energy, it is noteworthy that the rise in the total number of electrons, as well as the difference in the atomic radii of S, Se, and Te atoms, contributed to the increase in the volume of the crystal unit cell (see Table 2). As a result, due to the decrease in bulk modulus (B_0), it can be said that the results of the present investigation are in the right direction because it is familiar that the volume (V) is inversely proportionate to the bulk modulus (B_0).

3.2. Thermodynamic features

To design materials with enhanced thermodynamic features it is

Table 2

The calculated lattice constants a and c , volume V_0 , bulk modulus B_0 , pressure derivative of bulk modulus B' , and the total energy E_0 for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ compared to CZTX type compounds (with X: S, Se and Te).

Lattice parameters	$\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$	$\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$	$\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$	$\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$	$\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$	$\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnTe}_4$
a (Å)	5.8551	5.427 [39]	6.0903	5.606 [39]	6.5190	6.1834 [40]
c (Å)	11.1235	10.854 [39]	11.6824	11.212 [39]	12.4273	12.363 [40]
B_0 (GPa)	58.214	72.802 [40]	50.6864	66.757 [40]	39.9977	41.552 [40]
B' (GPa)	4.8502	–	5.6403	–	5.0126	–
V_0 (Å ³)	95.3783	–	108.3320	–	132.0352	–
E (Ryd)	-40117.925	–	-56365.985	–	-91299.242	–

significant to check the temperature and pressure-dependent thermal parameters, like bulk modulus B_0 , heat capacity (C_V) and thermal expansion coefficient (α). In this section, the Debye's quasi-harmonic model has been applied in the Gibbs code [52–54] to enumerate the thermodynamic features of the $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X: S, Se, Te) materials over a temperature array of 0–550 K and in the pressure array of 0–12 GPa as given in Figs. 3–6. The calculated results of volume-dependent temperature have been shown in Fig. 3 in the pressure range 0–12 GPa. One can see that the volume of the elementary cell is almost constant below 50 K, after this temperature, it increases monotonously for all studied compounds $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$. This indicates that at high temperatures, anharmonic effects play a prominent role, whereas the volume of the elementary cell decreases with an increase in pressure, as shown in Fig. 3. So, we can say that these are the three selected kesterite compounds $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$, which expand easily on heating. On the other hand, the results of temperature and pressure dependence of the bulk modulus B for all three selected compounds have been plotted in Fig. 4. The examination of this curve shows that the bulk modulus B remains constant below the temperature of 40 K. But above this temperature, the bulk modulus reduces with an increase in temperature at a specified pressure, while B_0 rises with the increase in pressure P at a specified temperature. However, in the case of these selected materials, the influence of pressure on B_0 is much more significant than that of

Fig. 2. The variation of total energy with volume of kesterites (a) $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, (b) $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and (c) $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ using GGA approximation.

Fig. 3. The cell volume change with temperature at 0–12 GPa pressures for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se and Te).

Fig. 4. The variation of the bulk modulus B_0 with temperature at different pressures for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se and Te).

temperature.

The heat capacity of a substance represents a strong point for understanding the thermal reactivity and intermolecular vibrations of substances, as well as numerous uses. The variations of the heat

capacities C_v with the temperature at 0–12 GPa pressures have been presented in Fig. 5 for all quaternary chalcogenide compounds $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X: S, Se, Te). It is understandable from Fig. 5 that temperature and pressure have reverse effects on heat capacity. The influence of

Fig. 5. The changes of constant volume heat capacity (C_v) with temperature at 0–12 GPa pressures for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se and Te).

Fig. 6. The variation of Debye temperature θ_D with temperature at different pressures for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X: S, Se and Te).

temperature on heat capacity is more important than pressure's. Further, the constant volume heat capacities C_v are proportional to T^3 , which follows the Debye model. Note that at $T = 0$ K, the constant volume heat capacity (C_v) is zero for these three kesterite compounds and the constant volume heat capacity (C_v) rises rapidly with the increase of the temperature until about $T = 500$ K, in which the curves approach and tend towards the Dulong–Petit limit [55]. The value of C_v is 197 J/molK for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$. In contrast, C_v is 198 J/molK for other two kesterites $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and AgInGaTe_4 . This indicates that the thermal energy stimulates all phonon modes at high temperatures, which is mutual to entire solids at high temperatures.

The Debye characteristic temperature θ_D is considered a thermal parameter characterized by the behavior of the thermal capacity of the studied solids. We can say that Debye temperature is defined as the maximum temperature that causes the normal vibration of the lattice atoms. The Debye characteristic temperature D changes with the temperature and pressure have been visualized in Fig. 6 for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X: S, Se and Te) compounds. The heat capacity and Debye characteristic temperature of the selected $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X: S, Se and Te) are tabulated in Table 3 at room temperature ($T = 300$ K) and zero (0) pressure. The Debye characteristic temperature decreases as the temperature rises, but it rises with the increase of pressure. Additionally, the results of Debye temperature remain constant at low temperatures ($T < 50$ K) for the selected kesterites. Ultimately, these results indicate that the Debye quasi-harmonic model confirms efficient calculation of the contribution of thermal vibrations to the thermodynamic function of a crystal. In addition, the behavior of the Debye characteristic temperature curves is similar to that of the compressibility modulus for their fluctuations with temperature and pressure.

3.3. Electronic features

Investigation of the crystal and electronic structures of $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ is needed to understand the origin of the physicochemical features and investigate the efficiency of their optoelectronic properties for use in solar cells and thermal power applications. Therefore, in this work, the electronic structure evaluations along with band structure and density of states for all the selected materials were implemented with the help of the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) within the modified Becke–Johnson (mBJ) potential (mBJ-GGA) [45,46]. It later proved to be a promising tool for mapping vacancies of electronic structures. These gaps are close to the experimental gaps, at low cost [56], for a large family of semiconductors and insulators [57]. The band path for specific symmetry points in k-space has been extracted from the suggested Brillouin zone of the kesterite structure as interpreted in Fig. 7 [58]. The calculated electronic band structures are illustrated in Fig. 8 [(a), (b) & (c)] for all selected compounds $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$.

However, these materials present semiconductor behavior with a direct bandgap at $\Gamma-\Gamma$, with 1.9 eV, 1.1 eV, and 0.86 eV values for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$, and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$, respectively. It is well known that Te and Se atoms are more negative than S atoms, which is why the band value of $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ is higher than that of the other two compounds, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$. As clearly stated, there is no data available to compare with the current studied compounds as these are new studies, only for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ our calculated bandgap energies (1.9 eV) match strongly with the theoretical predictions (1.72 eV) given recently

Table 3

The heat capacity at constant volume C_v and the Debye characteristic temperature θ_D at $T = 300$ K and at zero (0) pressure for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X: S, Se and Te).

Material	C_v	θ_D
$\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$	189.83761	301.27
$\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$	193.35407	239.05
$\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$	195.25911	198.23

Fig. 7. Brillouin zone of the space group $I\bar{4}2d$ for the $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ -like kesterite unit cell with special high symmetry points highlighted in orange [58]. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

by Gao et al. [34]. Nevertheless, it is reliable to choose the homologous array of kesterite light absorber compounds $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnX}_4$ (CZTX; X = S, Se, and Te) as an example for comparison. Because of their similar crystalline structure, these compounds represent the.

Majority of candidates used to fabricate multi-junction solar cells. Table 4 shows the presently calculated results at different k-points of the valence band maxima (VBM) and conduction band minima (CBM) values, as well as the band gap energies of the $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ compounds compared to available experimental and theoretical data of (CZTX; X = S, Se, and Te) semiconductors. The band gap energies obtained using the GGA-mBJ method closely align with previous experimental predictions and theoretical findings regarding CZTX compounds. Notably, in the case of the studied selenium kesterite phase $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$, the band gap has been found around 1.1 eV paired with a significant absorption coefficient of approximately $10,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. These results indicate that $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ holds considerable potential for use as the absorber layer in kesterite solar cells, whereas for sulfide kesterite phase $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ the energy gap is equal to 1.9 eV which is a more promising candidate than the first one to be used in the top cell of a multiple junctions thin film solar cell in which the ideal band gap for the top cell is situated between 1.6 eV up 2 eV. However, it is well known that the calculated band gaps from the TB-mBJ functional are more accurate than the GGA-PBE functional and agree with experiments with a typical discrepancy of less than 10 % for certain semiconductors and insulators, but some limitations can also be seen on simple applications of the TB-mBJ method to other materials that still encounter significant difficulties because of the insufficient treatment of the localized d electrons [36,40].

To describe the chemical bonding behavior and to elucidate the participating orbitals of compounds, it is crucial to discuss the electronic density of states (total density TDOS and partial PDOS) as a representative case given in Fig. 9(a) and (b) and (c), for kesterite-type $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ & $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ semiconductors, respectively. It was found from the electronic band structure that all chalcogenides quaternary compounds $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se, Te) have a semiconductor nature, with the band gaps energies of 0.9 eV, 1.1 eV, and 1.9 eV for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ & $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$, respectively. At low-level energies of the DOS, the band ranges from -13 eV to -11.6 eV and is dominated by the s states of the S and Se atoms for three compounds $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$. The band found in the interval $[-6.50 \text{ eV}; -5.60 \text{ eV}]$ is strongly composed of the atomic states of the In and Ga atoms for the three studied quaternary compounds. Then, the valence band (VB) situated at the range $[-5.5; E_F]$, contains mainly a hybridization of the

Fig. 8. The band structures of (a) $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, (b) $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and (c) $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ using GGA + mBJ approximations.

Table 4

The valence band maxima (VBM) as well as the conduction band minima (CBM) positions of $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S, Se, Te}$).

k-points	$\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$		$\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$		$\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$	
	VBM	CBM	VBM	CBM	VBM	CBM
Γ	-0.0076	1.9090	0.0065	1.1180	-0.0002	0.8678
X	-0.3014	2.9124	-0.3416	2.1122	-0.4479	1.3554
Z	-0.6317	3.4322	-0.7352	2.6976	-0.9395	1.7062
N	-0.1740	3.2262	-0.2860	2.6024	-0.4602	2.0359
P	-0.3484	3.0204	-0.4583	2.3227	-0.6561	1.6044
E_g (eV)						
Present work	1.9166		1.1115		0.868	
DFT	1.72 [34]		-		-	
CZTX \rightarrow						
	$\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$		$\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$		$\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnTe}_4$	
Expt	1.46, 1.50, 1.51 [36]		1.0, 1.40–1.65 [36]		0.84–0.88 [37]	
DFT	0.91 [36], 1.47 [38] 1.50 [39], 0.65 [40]		0.54 [36], 0.90 [38] 0.96 [39], 0.28 [40]		0.47 [36], 0.32 [40]	

d states of the Ag atom and p states of the X atoms ($X = \text{S, Se, and Te}$). Finally, at high-level energies, the conduction bands (CB) primarily contribute by hybridizing the s and p states of the In and Ga atoms.

It is worth noting that most of the research work has been done on

homologous quaternary chalcogenide materials of type $\text{I}_2\text{-II-IV-VI}_4$ (CZTX ($X = \text{S, Se, and Te}$)). Consequently, the comparison to most research and work given on homologue quaternary chalcogenide compounds is crucial because these materials are similar to selected compounds $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S, Se, and Te}$). This is confirmed by the results of our findings and as mentioned by others studies [34,36–41] that going from the tellurides to the selenides with larger lattice constants and higher p orbital energies, the band gap is generally much smaller than for the sulphides [see Table 4].

3.4. Optical and optical thin film features

Recently, numerous academics have examined and optimized the optical and electrical features of photovoltaic systems, where the best efficiencies have been achieved using good absorbent materials by improving the essential constraints including the band gap of semiconductors with good absorption coefficients, attractive attention to the solar spectrum and good stability in contrast to solar irradiation [12]. To achieve these results, the investigation of semiconductors occupying the kesterite type chalcogenides quaternary compounds $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S, Se, and Te}$) is of relevant concern for their utilizations in photovoltaic systems and optoelectronic devices. In particular, these materials displays stimulating features such as calculated band gaps around 1.5 eV, a value that improved matches with the extreme solar spectrum

Fig. 9. Total and projected electron densities of states of quaternary chalcogenides type kesterite compounds (a) $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, (b) $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and (c) $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ using GGA approximation.

conversion for photovoltaic equipment. To complement these findings, we have extensively tested, performed and discussed the optical properties as well as optical thin film characteristics on three above mentioned compounds $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S}, \text{Se}, \text{and Te}$) given in the following section.

The frequency-dependent complex dielectric function $\epsilon(\omega) = \epsilon_1(\omega) + i\epsilon_2(\omega)$ is a well-established model for describing the optical properties of a material. The imaginary portion $\epsilon_2(\omega)$ has been resolved by computing the electronic structure employing the joint density of states and the optical matrix elements [59–64]. The real part of the dielectric tensor $\epsilon_1(\omega)$ can be calculated from $\epsilon_2(\omega)$ using the Kramers–Krönig relationship [65,66]. Then, the other optical properties can be borrowed from $\epsilon_1(\omega)$ and $\epsilon_2(\omega)$, such as the absorption coefficient $\alpha(\omega)$, refractive index $n(\omega)$, and the reflectivity $R(\omega)$ [59–64]. Due to the tetragonal structure of the kesterite structure ($a = b \neq c$), all-optical spectra have been enumerated at the equilibrium lattice constant using the GGA-mBJ method along both directions of light polarization (xx) and (zz) as presented in Figs. 10–15.

Fig. 10 shows the calculated dispersive real dielectric function ϵ_1 for the energy range up to 16 eV for all $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ compounds. From these curves, one can notice that they have almost the same contrast. The calculated static dielectric constant values are $\epsilon_1^{xx}(0) = 5.193$ and $\epsilon_1^{zz} = 5.11$ for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ and $\epsilon_1^{xx}(0) = 6.736$ and $\epsilon_1^{zz} = 6.639$ for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\epsilon_1^{xx}(0) = 9.084$ and $\epsilon_1^{zz} = 8.826$ for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ along both directions of light polarization (xx) and (zz) (Table 5).

Since, going from $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4 \rightarrow \text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4 \rightarrow \text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ and regarding their calculated band gaps of 1.916 eV, 1.111 eV, and 0.868 eV, respectively, we can confirm that the calculated static dielectric functions tend to increase with decreasing band gap. Further, we can see that below the frequency 6 eV for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, 5 eV for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and 3.5 eV for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$, the compounds present a high permittivity, then above these frequencies, one can notice a rapid decrease in the result of the real portion of real dielectric constant which it exceeds zero starting from 8.2 eV for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, 7.7 eV for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and 4.8 eV for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$.

Fig. 10. Real dielectric function along xx and zz directions for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se and Te).

Fig. 11. The imaginary dielectric function along xx and zz directions for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se, Te).

The imaginary dielectric function enumerated with GGA-mBJ is shown in Fig. 11 for the selected materials. To explain the absorptions that have been depicted in these spectra, it is necessary to deliberate transitions from occupied to unoccupied bands in electronic energy

Fig. 12. The absorption coefficient $\alpha(\omega)$ along xx and zz directions for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se, and Te).

Fig. 13. The extinction coefficient $k(\omega)$ and refractive index $n(\omega)$ using an effective polycrystalline dielectric constant approach for quaternary chalcogenide semiconductors $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se and Te).

band structure, expressly at high symmetry points in the Brillouin zone. Where the first one starts from the energy gap values called threshold energy E_0 , approximately at 1.97 eV, 1.12 eV, and 0.857 eV for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$, and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$, respectively, which originates predominantly from the transitions of electrons in $\Gamma - \Gamma$ directions. In the absorptive part, several stronger peaks appeared at 5.9 eV and 7 eV

Fig. 14. The Seebeck coefficient S changes with temperature for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S, Se and Te}$).

Fig. 15. The electrical conductivity σ versus temperature for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S, Se and Te}$) semiconductors.

Table 5

The static results of the real dielectric function ϵ_1 and refractive index n for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S, Se, Te}$) along both directions of the incident radiations polarization.

	$\epsilon_1^{xx}(0)$	$\epsilon_1^{zz}(0)$	$n^{xx}(0)$	$n^{zz}(0)$
$\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$	5.1936	5.1108	2.2789	2.2607
$\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$	6.7367	6.6391	2.5955	2.5766
$\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$	9.0841	8.8263	3.0139	2.9709

for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, 5.26 eV and 6.43 eV for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ as well as for the third compound $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ at 4.58 eV and 3.44 eV in both directions of the incident radiations polarization ϵ_2^{xx} and ϵ_2^{zz} components separately. The peaks are created from the transitions d -Ag and p -X ($X: \text{S, Se \& Te}$) electron states situated at the top of the valence bands to the empty s -In, p -Ga with p -s electron states governing the bottom of the conduction bands. At the low energy range, the spectra don't display significant anisotropy in both directions (parallel and perpendicular to the c -axis) and all three semiconductors could be considered isotopes at this energy level. Fig. 12 illustrates the absorption coefficient of $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ compounds ($X = \text{S, Se, Te}$). From these curves, we can see that at the frequencies that approximately correspond to the gap energy value (band gap), the absorption coefficient curves increase rapidly until reaching

the maximum in the energy range 8 eV-12 eV for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and from 6 eV to 10 eV for the third compound $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$. This means that our compounds revealed strong absorption phenomena in this interval. In our study of the optical coating properties of the selected compounds, we suggest averaging the values measured both parallel and perpendicular to the c -axis. This average holds significance, as highlighted by Rignanese et al. [67]. To corroborate our computational results regarding the optical coating features, we will employ an effective estimation of the polycrystalline dielectric constant, as outlined by Petousis et al. [68]. The equation for this is given by:

$$\epsilon_{poly} = \frac{3\lambda_1\lambda_2\lambda_3}{\lambda_1\lambda_2 + \lambda_1\lambda_3 + \lambda_2\lambda_3}$$

Here λ_i = the eigenvalues of the enumerated dielectric tensor.

The refractive index is enumerated by captivating the square root of the mean of the eigenvalues of the electronic dielectric tensor.

Fig. 13 indicates the refractive indices and the extinction coefficients dependent on photon energy for the $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S, Se, Te}$) as polycrystalline semiconductors. It should be noticed that there is a remarkable similarity between the spectra of different compounds in the energy region, except for a minor spectral deviation due to the difference in their band gap energies. It is depicted that below 6 eV, the refractive index reaches high values, which means that the chosen compounds have a strong ability to slow down and refract light, and this point is pertinent for semiconductor compounds. Above this frequency, the curves of all three quaternary chalcogenide compounds decrease to small values. Furthermore, the refractive indices of $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ are higher than that of $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$. It rises with energy in the absorption section, attaining a peak in the ultraviolet at around 3 eV. Then, it reduces to the lowest level at 12.5 eV. The simulated static refractive indices $n(0)$ have been originated to have the values of 2.272, 2.589, and 2.999 for all polycrystalline semiconductors $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$, respectively. These values are close to those calculated in both directions perpendicular and parallel to the c axis as collected in Table 5. The extinction coefficient $k(\omega)$ spectra are visualized in Fig. 13, where several maxima happen after the optical band gap energy and the origin of these structures is well discussed in the imaginary portion of the dielectric function.

Thin-film solar cells adapt sunlight into electricity using a thin layer of photovoltaic (PV) substance in place of traditional silicon cells, which have become more popular all over the world. Thin-film modules are available in both rigid and flexible versions and each type has its advantages and disadvantages. Among them, kesterite-based copper zinc tin selenide (CZTSe) and copper zinc tin sulphide (CZTS) thin films have fascinated significant care as capable substances for sustainable and cost-effective thin-film solar cells [12]. Nevertheless, the fruitful amalgamation of these substances into photovoltaic devices is affected by some parameters, for example: changes in solar radiation and quality of materials, which require increasing the absorption capacity of materials to improve overall display efficiency. The purpose of this study is to clarify the optical coating behaviors of new kesterite-type chalcogenides quaternary compounds $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S, Se, Te}$) using the matrix theory [69–71] where each layer is represented by a 2×2 matrix, comprising layer thickness and complex wavelength reliant on refractive index obtained via FP-LAPW calculations [42–48]. Hence, this calculation can be used to determine the amplitude of absorbance (A), reflectance (R), and transmittance (T) as illustrated in Figs.S1-S2-S3 (in supporting information).

Using both estimated processes of deposition: first on a clear substrate (glasses: $n_{glasses} = 1.5$, $k_{glasses} = 0$) and second on a free-standing layer ($n_{air} = 1$, $k_{air} = 0$) at different thicknesses in the wavelength range from 100 nm to 1000 nm, 1200 nm up 1600 nm for thin films $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$, respectively. The absorbance spectra (refer to Fig. S1 (a), (b), and (c)) reveal that as the layer thickness increases beyond 1000 nm, the $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ thin films exhibit enhanced absorbance, achieving approximately 80 % and 70 %, respectively.

respectively. These films effectively encompass a broad spectrum of electromagnetic radiation, particularly in the visible range (from 0.4 μm to 0.7 μm). This trend is observed in both coating procedures: when layers are applied to a transparent substrate and when they are free-standing. In contrast, the $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ thin film displays a marked reduction in absorbance within the visible and near-infrared (IR) wavelengths. These consequences match earlier experimental predictions and theoretical findings [1–41] of CZTX compounds. Most materials are used in solar cell applications. The analysis of the effective spectral variations in absorbance versus wavelength for the compounds $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$, all of which possess a kesterite structure, reveals important insights. These compounds exhibit direct band gaps of approximately 0.58–1.9 eV and display large absorption coefficients ($\alpha > 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). This evidence suggests that $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ are promising candidates for absorbing solar radiation, making them well-suited for photovoltaic applications such as solar cells. Whereas, the $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ compound is a more promising candidate to be used in the top cell of a multiple junctions thin film solar cell and also it exhibits greater potential for use in UV technology. The reflectance spectra plotted against wavelength are presented in Fig. S2 (a), (b), and (c). The data presented in Fig. S2 indicates that the reflectance of all the thin films remains below 60 %, suggesting that the selected materials exhibit low reflectance values. Nonetheless, these semiconductors hold promise as anti-reflection coatings for a variety of technological applications, including video screens and camera lenses. The transmittance spectrum of all three $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ thin films is shown in Figs. S3(a), (b), and (c). It is seen from Fig. S3 that the transmittance was found to be generally low in almost all the regions of electromagnetic spectrum for the both selected materials $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ using a thicker layer (more than 1000 nm). Our estimated absorber layer thickness up to 1600 nm = 1.6 μm for the studied compounds align well with the most used absorber layers for flexible CZTSe (1.5–2 μm) and CISE (~2 μm) thin-film solar cells as reported by Li et al. [13]. It is evident from Fig. S3 of the absorbance spectra that these materials can potentially be as good absorbers in thin film solar cells.

3.5. Thermoelectric features

Nowadays, hybridizing photovoltaic (PV) and thermoelectric (TE) technology devices are inspected as perfect for effectively harnessing solar energy. The combination of both systems (PV-TE) is very important which adapts solar power into electricity through the photovoltaic (PV) effect of solar cells, which concurrently produces electricity by the Seebeck effect of the thermoelectric (TE) equipment based on the excess heat of solar cells, which subsequently provides the maximum (or near maximum) power output [72–75]. Due to their exceptional compensations, PV-TE systems have arisen in the previous decade as a capable substitute among other green energy generation technologies. By the way, the studies focused on the design of a photovoltaic-thermo-electric hybrid system, which resulted in the contribution of numerous new academics in cracking various thermoelectric issues. The investigation is most active in thermoelectricity, mainly aimed at improving the thermoelectric efficiency ZT of identified and novel thermoelectric compounds [76,77].

Because of these matters, this subunit liberates and appraises the potential of new kesterites-type quaternary chalcogenides ($\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$) as a substitute for current thermoelectric substances. By using Boltztrap code [78], we have investigated the thermoelectric features, for example, electrical and thermal conductivity, Seebeck coefficient, and figure of merit as schematized in Figs. 14–17. Via definition, the Seebeck coefficient specifies the ability of a substance to reverse a gradient temperature to voltage [79–83]. The estimated Seebeck coefficients of all studied quaternary chalcogenides semiconductors are given in Fig. 14.

We remark that the Seebeck coefficient is optimistic for the whole

Fig. 16. The thermal conductivity κ changes with temperature for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S, Se and Te}$).

Fig. 17. Figure of merit of $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ ($X = \text{S, Se, and Te}$).

temperature array, indicating that the conduction of these semiconductors is p -type because the charge carriers are holes. A decent thermoelectric substance has an advanced value of the Seebeck coefficient and figure of merit. At lower temperatures ($\approx 100 \text{ K}$), the Seebeck coefficient shows a higher value for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ in comparison to $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ compounds. Then, the figure of merit rises as the temperature until it attains an extreme value of around 450 K in two materials, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$, and at 800 K in $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$. At room temperature ($T = 300 \text{ K}$), the values of Seebeck coefficient of 212.3593 $\mu\text{V/K}$, 204.520 $\mu\text{V/K}$ and 152.4252 $\mu\text{V/K}$ for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$, and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$, correspondingly. It is well known that for a potential thermoelectric substance, advanced Seebeck coefficient and electrical conductivity are predictable for advanced power factor, nevertheless, their coexistence is fairly infrequent. In addition, the evaluation of transport properties of these systems showed reasonable Seebeck coefficient ($\sim 120 \mu\text{V/K}$ to $200 \mu\text{V/K}$) compared to those of Bi_2Te_3 , Sb_2Te_3 compounds and based-alloys especially in the low temperature range. These thermoelectric (TE) materials are the most widely studied and have been the most employed materials in large-scale industries, namely in refrigerators, power generators, and thermal sensors [84–90].

Besides, the electrical conductivity characterizes the flux of free charge carriers; the plot of the dissimilarity of this parameter under temperature effect is given in Fig. 15. It is seen that the electrical conductivity is very small at low temperatures which is consistent with a

high Seebeck coefficient indicating the insulator behavior of these compounds. Then it rises with the temperature and attains a value of 1.2×10^{19} (1/s cm Ω) at high temperature and this one again reveals the semiconductor behavior. At room temperature, the values of electrical conductivity are as follows: 3.207382×10^{18} (1/s cm Ω), 3.290982×10^{18} (1/s cm Ω), 4.059912×10^{18} (1/s cm Ω) for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$, respectively. According to resemblances in the crystal structure and electronic features of CZTSSe compounds to the studied kesterite $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ type compounds. The obtained results show a systematic agreement with recent studies given in the literature [11], [91–92] of CZTX compounds. Most materials are used in solar cell and thermoelectric applications.

The heat conduction is excited by phonon (lattice vibration) and electrons in materials; in this work, the estimated thermoelectric parameters are determined by the use of Boltztrap code, which is based on the semi-classical Boltztrap transport theory and the rigid band method. This code computes only the electronic thermal conductivity because at high temperatures, the electronic thermal conductivity becomes principal, whereas at small temperatures, the phonon lattice thermal conductivity is the leading. Fig. 16 illustrates the calculated electronic thermal conductivity for kesterite-type chalcogenides $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se and Te). Following Fig. 16, the thermal conductivity rises with a temperature rise, and this is because increasing temperature increases the probability of interaction between electron-electron. The values of the electronic thermal conductivity have been found to equal: 6.2327×10^{13} (W/mKs), 5.8415×10^{13} (W/mKs) and 5.7388×10^{13} (W/mKs) for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ correspondingly.

Finally, the temperature dependence figure of merit ZT for a bulk sample of $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se, and Te) with a kesterite structure is shown in Fig. 17. The ZT s are very high for both compounds for the whole temperature array demonstrating that this semiconductor shows an effective high ZT in comparison to $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$.

This indicates promising materials have been utilized for thermoelectric applications. Hence, a sharp rise in the thermoelectric figure of merit is observed in both $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ (at 100 K from 0.2 in $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ and 0.002 in $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ to 0.75 in $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$ and 0.65 in $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$ at 700 K). This growth is mainly associated with a significant decrease in electrical resistance in a given temperature range. At 300 K the ZT values are 0.6962, 0.70695, and 0.49309 for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$, respectively, while at 1000 K the ZT values are 0.7476, 0.7588 and 0.7342 for $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$, respectively. Overall, an enhanced and different values of ZT for Bi_2Te_3 and Sb_2Te_3 are reported in literature [84–89] which can be attributed to the different synthetic methods employed, more recently the highest ZT values of 0.7 (at 573 K) and 0.9 (at 523 K) for n-type Bi_2Te_3 and p-type Sb_2Te_3 , respectively were achieved by Hamawandi et al. [90] that are close to our simulated ZT of 0.75 for both $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ studied compounds.

Finally, the power factor (PF) plays a pivotal role to ensure the efficiency of any thermoelectric material; $\text{PF} = S^2\sigma$ where S is Seebeck coefficient and σ is electrical conductivity. Fig. 18 illustrates the power factor vs temperature for all studied compounds $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaS}_4$, $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaTe}_4$. At low temperature the PF shows lower values and displays an increasing trend along with increasing temperature, which means that these compounds could be good materials for thermoelectricity. The room temperature (300 K) value of PF for the $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se, Te) are respectively 14.46×10^{10} W/m K^2 s, 1.3765×10^{10} W/m K^2 s, and 9.432×10^{10} W/m K^2 s. Those values increase to 47.78×10^{10} W/m K^2 s, 55.369×10^{10} W/m K^2 s, 57.990×10^{10} W/m K^2 s for all aforementioned compounds respectively at higher temperature up 1000 K. The increasing behavior of the power factor in these systems can be attributed to increased electrical conductivity because the PF is directly related to electrical conductivity. Consequently, the aforementioned materials possessing a high-power factor indicating that could be favorable candidates for thermo power energy.

Fig. 18. Power factor PF of $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se, and Te).

4. Conclusions

By using computational methods, our findings demonstrate significant improvements in studying and predefining structural, optoelectronic and transport properties of novel kesterite type quaternary chalcogenide materials, which would be used in a truly predictive manner to guide synthesis and offer valuable insights for researchers and engineers to access their outstanding properties, and hence suggesting directions for future research, emphasizing the critical role of these compounds in advancing engineering and technological applications. Based on the conducted results and analysis, the following key findings and conclusions have been drawn:

- For the first time, quaternary chalcogenide compounds with a new I₂-III-III-VI₄ formula class, such as $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaX}_4$ (X = S, Se, Te) in the kesterite structure, were predicted using the Wien2k simulation code.
- The investigated materials' structural, thermodynamic, optical coating, optoelectronic, and thermoelectric properties were predicted using the ab initio FP-LAPW method with the PBE-GGA + mBJ approach for exchange-correlation potentials.
- These compounds exhibit semiconducting behavior with a direct bandgap at the Γ -point, making them suitable candidates for optoelectronic applications such as solar cells. The bandgap width ($E_g = 1.0\text{--}1.9$ eV) aligns well with ideal values for effectively capturing a broad solar spectrum.
- High electronic mobility of charge carriers and a significant absorption coefficient (greater than 10^4cm^{-1} in the visible region) highlight their potential for LED applications, such as photodetectors and solar cells.
- The predicted results are in favorable agreement with experimental measurements for analogous kesterite CZTS compounds.
- For achieving optimal absorbance levels, higher layer thicknesses up to 1600 nm are recommended, particularly in $\text{Ag}_2\text{InGaSe}_4$ thin films.
- The figure of merit (ZT) reached an impressive value of ~ 0.70 , indicating strong potential as a p-type semiconductor material.
- These findings suggest that the studied compounds hold promise as multifunctional materials for applications in photovoltaics, thermoelectrics, and other optoelectronic technologies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

C. Bourahla: Formal analysis, Software, Data curation, Validation.
F. Chiker: Software, Formal analysis, Resources, Data curation. **H. Khachai:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Formal analysis, Writing

– review & editing, Visualization, Resources, Data curation. **R. Khenata:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Investigation, Data curation. **A. Bouhemadou:** Data curation, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Supervision. **Devraj Singh:** Software, Data curation, Resources. **S. Bin-Omran:** Visualization, Formal analysis, Validation, Data curation. **R.D. Eithiraj:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Hamad R. Jappor:** Visualization, Formal analysis, Validation, Data curation. **Saleem A. Khan:** Visualization, Validation, Data curation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpics.2025.112970>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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